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I. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This deliverable serves as the initial collection of tools and services aimed at supporting software quality and FAIRness within scientific research communities. The initial collection of existing tools and services is provided in digital formats to enable continuous updates. A snapshot is attached at the end of this deliverable. This document is intended for use across the EOSC Science Clusters, facilitating efforts to assess, curate, and enhance the quality and FAIRness of research software. Various methods were used to collect the tools. Subsequently, they were classified into the quality dimensions of sustainability, FAIR and open software. The initial tool collection contains 77 entries covering all quality dimensions and attributes. The majority of tools listed are applicable universally via the various EOSC Science Clusters.

II. Introduction

The EVERSE project aims to create a framework for Research Software and code excellence, collaboratively designed and championed by the research communities across five EOSC Science Clusters and national Research Software Expertise Centres, in pursuit of building a European network of Research Software Quality and setting the foundations of a future Virtual Institute for Research Software Excellence.

As part of the EVERSE project, Work Package 3 (WP3) aims to connect existing individual tools and services with developers and EOSC Science Clusters [1] in three steps:

1. collecting existing tools and services for software (including all forms of executable code) quality,
2. linking them in common pipelines or frameworks, and
3. integrating them with platforms used in the EOSC Science Clusters.

As an initial step, Deliverable 3.1 provides a first collection of existing tools and services usable in the EOSC Science Clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality. This initial collection will form the basis for future work planned throughout the course of the EVERSE project. In a next step (M8), the collected tools and services will be evaluated in the form of a workshop against initial best practices from WP2.

The *EOSC Task Force Ensure Software Quality* [2] report defines software quality as a series of desirable characteristics that are required for improving computer programs, meaning that they are well adapted to their purpose, generate reproducible and correct results, highly available, or possess other properties that contribute to their robustness. In other words, software quality is the degree to which a software meets its requirements and fulfils the needs of its intended users. The scope of the quality measures or "good-enough" practices to be implemented is based on the three-tier model of software [3]: Analysis Code, Prototype Tools and Research Software Infrastructure. Software quality tools and services are considered to be those that assist researchers or research software engineers in implementing specific quality attributes for their research software projects. There are two different types of software quality tools: on one hand, there are tools and services that enable the assessment or evaluation of certain quality attributes, on the other hand there are tools that help maintain or enhance these attributes. A tool that evaluates Research Software in terms of how well it implements the FAIR4RS principles falls under the first category. An example of the second category is a tool that specifically supports the publication of each release of a software in a repository.

In this deliverable we first describe the methods used to collect, classify and organize the existing tools and services usable within the EOSC Science Clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness in [Section III](#). Various digital tools and methods were used to obtain an initial overview as comprehensive as possible. Based on this, [Section IV](#) describes the results determined for the attributes of the identified quality dimensions. The initial list of tools and services is available in a separate digital document, which will become part of the RSQKit [4] in the future. Research Software Quality Kit (RSQKit), developed as part of [EVERSE project](#), contains a collection of curated training resources, tools and guidelines on research software quality that align, adapt, and extend to the specific needs of various research communities. A short summary and next steps can be found in the conclusion ([Section V](#)) of this document.

III. Methodology

This section details the process for collecting and organizing existing tools and services usable within Science clusters to assess, curate, and improve software quality and FAIRness. Our methodology included collaborative tool collection, expert input, and quality aspects definition, following these key steps.

1. Initial Data Collection through Collaborative Miro Board

An initial data collection was conducted through a collaborative Miro board [8], designed as an interactive space where members of EVERSE contributed insights on relevant tools and practices. Whether a tool is to be considered relevant was initially decided by the participants themselves. This has been instrumental not only to converge on first sets of data, but also to build a shared understanding between EVERSE partners regarding the purpose and application of software quality tools in scientific projects.

The board was structured into distinct sections — use cases, user personas, quality practices, Research Software levels and tools — allowing participants to systematically document and share their knowledge.

In the first monthly call with EVERSE partners, a brainstorming session was employed to gather feedback from the participants on the key aspects of the issues at hand. This method allowed us to have access to a preliminary dataset, enhancing inclusion of the wider EVERSE community and diversity of input. This set of data highlighted a first collection of software quality practices, and a set of user personas (see Figure 1 and Figure 2Figure 2.).

Quality practise	Q1	Q2
CODING PLATFORM	gitlab, github, social coding platform, Issue collector, Repository setup template, contributor guidelines, GitHub Insights, actively maintained	Gitlab CI, GitHub actions CI/CD, jekyll, Github
SOURCE CODE AUTHORING	code review, codestyles, code writing assistants / help	VS code editor + plugins, copilot, chatGPT, stackoverflow
VERSION CONTROL	version control, repository	pre-commit, Git, GitLens
DOCUMENTATION	documentation, Documentation assessment, code documentation, automatic documentation	readthedocs, sphinx, Docuaurus, ChangeLog
LICENSING	licensing, guidelines, open source	Tortellini, REUSE license checker
STATIC ANALYSIS	code analysis tools, security scanning, code complexity checker, dependency management, SBOMs, linting	mypy, pylint, black, SonarQube static code analysis
PROFILING	energy efficiency, performance, observability, accuracy assessment, profiling	Lightrun, cProfile, memory-profiler, Valgrind (for C++), Metric tracking Weights and Biases
TESTING AND CONTINUOUS INTEGRATION	continuous integration, CI/CD, test tools, test coverage checker, unit tests, test data	pytest, JUNIT
PACKAGING AND DISTRIBUTING	packaging, containerisation, container registry, containers	Docker/singularity containers, Dockerhub, language dependent software repositories (e.g. Docker Hub, PyPI, Maven)
SCIENTIFIC PUBLICATION	publishing, citation	Zenodo, Zotero, PaperWithCode, bio.tools
FAIRNESS	Check FAIRNESS	howfairis
SECURITY	security scanning, Public vs private Git repos	GitHub's Dependabot

Figure 1.1 Miro board results of the task: “What is a tool that your organisation/project is using to increase software quality?” (Q1) and “What do you associate with tools and services for software quality and FAIRness?” (Q2).

User roles	Brief description and personas	High level use cases
 Researcher (who code)		<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 15%;">code publishers: is my code up to standard xy</div> <div style="width: 15%;">User (that a developer): How to use somebody else's code? (Citizen? License?)</div> <div style="width: 15%;">Involvement of research community and academic: How useful are the EVERSE technology watch to check if they connect the tools & services</div> <div style="width: 15%;">Other projects: to add their views - how open is this</div> <div style="width: 15%;">Bid writers: be informed about the future tools they should be using (e.g. AI tools)</div> <div style="width: 15%;">Researcher: overview and comparison between each tools to help editors improve their code</div> </div>
		<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 15%;">code developers & researchers: developing code based on best practices & tools to support their everyday routine</div> <div style="width: 15%;">Researchers: how can we work up to date with current developments/technologies, e.g. particularly in which for rapid changes</div> <div style="width: 15%;">Developer: Is there any guidelines/rules to follow to make my code FAIR?</div> <div style="width: 15%;">researcher/RSE/developer: discover tools and services they can use for their own analysis/research/work</div> <div style="width: 15%;">A place I can point people to when they have any doubt regarding how to assist a given use practice quality.</div> <div style="width: 15%;">search for best practices & relevant tools to use</div> </div>
 RSE		<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 12%;">RSE: what steps can I take to further improve the code?</div> <div style="width: 12%;">RSE: What are others using to distribute their software to the community?</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Developer: what is considered best practice</div> <div style="width: 12%;">RSE: what tools shall I use in my next project?</div> <div style="width: 12%;">RSE: find tool for certain task (filtering for example)</div> <div style="width: 12%;">RSE: what is the next technology I should learn?</div> <div style="width: 12%;">RSE wanting guidance on the best tools for the job</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Software engineering researchers: what is the state of SQ in different domains</div> </div>
 Research Manager / PI		<div style="display: flex; justify-content: space-between;"> <div style="width: 12%;">PI: check that their tech team is using fairly up to date technology</div> <div style="width: 12%;">project manager: should we develop our own software package or stay for existing services?</div> <div style="width: 12%;">project manager: how can we ensure that software lasts on a time scale longer than the developers' participation</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Institutions could use the EVERSE technology watch to assess the code of applicants for jobs in RSE</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Organisation using the technology watch as a means of guidance in terms of the technology that defines their organisation</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Research institutions: setup software quality framework internally</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Manager who controlling and maintaining software development work: how do we handle requirements on work</div> <div style="width: 12%;">Manager/Responsible in non-developing: wanting to know if the tools used for their research are still ones of the art</div> <div style="width: 12%;">manager: how to get current project to the next level</div> </div>
 RSQKIT editor		<div style="width: 100%;"> developer of a SQ service/tool: contribute to the technology watch </div>
 Industrial partner		
 Policy maker / EU commissioner		<div style="width: 100%;"> Policy maker: what best practices should be required in call </div>

Figure 2. Results of the task “How do you think a user of the EVERSE technology watch will want to use it? Put down the type of user, and the questions they want answered by the Technology Watch.” on a Miro board.

Based on the first results, a second call was organized where the data was augmented by analysing more specific use cases, and expanding their details in relation to specific personas, quality practices, research software level, and desirable metadata for the software quality tools (see Figure 2Figure 2.)

This initial exercise, internal to the EVERSE partnership, was essential to provide a common basis for reasoning about the applicability and usefulness of software quality tools in research software, and it enabled further reasoning by providing a reference framework [6].

In this session we will focus on **METADATA** for the EVERSE technology watch.
 For each item in the technology watch, there are certain characteristics and properties that we want to collect about it.
 A careful selection of metadata is essential in making sure that we can answer our users' needs.
 In this session you will be asked to expand one of the use case we have previously identify and reason about what metadata will make it possible.

Figure Arabi3. Results of the task to gather relevant metadata for the EVERSE technology watch on a Miro board. The initial use cases were expanded with one or more examples, associated Research Software quality aspects, eligible Research Software levels listed and required metadata to apply the target tool.

2. Survey and Workshops (SKAO and EVERSE)

Following the initial collection of tools via Miro board ([section III.1](#)), which focussed on requirements and use cases for software quality tools, a survey was designed as a next step. The aim was to gain a broader view, by including SKAO as well as the wider EVERSE community, and gather data on the usage, awareness and impact of software quality tools. The targeted audience for this survey was from the SKAO SRCNet collaboration and from within the EVERSE community. With both groups online workshops were conducted during which the survey was carried out and subsequently discussed.

Below are the essential goals that have been considered while designing the survey and running the workshops:

- Measure the level of awareness or knowledge of software quality tools among the target audience.
- Gain insights into the specific needs, preferences and challenges while selecting any software quality tools.
- Get opinions and perceptions around different aspects that are influencing and guiding the search for software quality tools.
- Collect software quality tools around the defined software quality attributes.
- Identify institutional and project involvement to promote software quality tools.
- Get feedback on the conduction of the survey and workshop.

1. Selection Criteria

- Criteria for choosing or selecting software quality tools involved various aspects like the publicly available documentation of the tool developer, community support, company or institute reputation, instructions on steps to install and/or setup the tool and its cross platform compatibility, user interface, reusability, computational efficiency, licensing information, information on data protection and security.
- Depending on the targeted audience with different roles in software development, the tool selection criteria was considered based on how the tool fulfils its purpose.

2. Data Collection Process

- Primary data around software quality tools was collected from the survey and subsequent discussions during the online workshops, which were conducted synchronously via zoom.
- Prior to running the survey an introduction was given to the audience about the goals of the EVERSE project and community, followed by a brief overview about the software quality tools survey. Afterwards, participants were given about twenty minutes to fill the responses.
- Google forms was chosen as the tool to create and distribute the questionnaire. It was ensured that the survey questions were clearly stated, unbiased (see point 4. below) and aligned with the objectives.
- So far the data collected is from people with different roles (as shown in Figure 2) from SKAO and EVERSE.
- The process of conducting surveys along with the survey questionnaire was the same in all repetitions.

- The format of a workshop was also chosen to continuously enhance the structure of the survey and the nature of the questions, as well as to discuss initial answers.

3. Data Analysis

- The survey responses were exported in spreadsheets leading towards first inspection of survey responses that included data cleaning and removal of duplicate entries. Later the same spreadsheets were used to analyse survey results.
- Graphs or charts were created for visualisation of gathered data. The findings around the results [8] were later presented within the EVERSE community for discussion.

4. Limitations/Bias

- The main target group of the surveys and workshops was initially focused on members of the EVERSE community and SKAO.
- Due to the high volatility of the tools used, the survey must be viewed as a continuous process.

3. Creation of a list of tools Spreadsheet for Tool Collection

Following the Miro Board and survey results discussion, a collaborative spreadsheet was developed to formalize the collection of tools identified. The spreadsheet served as the primary tool repository, cataloguing each tool's description, quality dimension, its software level, license, the EOSC Science Cluster and the URL link. A snapshot is attached at the end of this deliverable.

4. Definition and Categorization of Quality Dimensions

A comprehensive categorization of software quality aspects was essential for effectively classifying the outcomes from Miro board analyses and surveys. This categorization was built upon established standards, expert consultations, and relevant literature, ensuring an evidence-based and structured approach.

1. Quality Dimensions

To define the main quality dimensions, insights were derived from expert discussions and pivotal reports:

The EVERSE Task Force 2: Reference Model

The EVERSE Reference Model outlines a structured framework for understanding software quality. This model considers different perspectives depending on the software type, life cycle stage, and user roles, emphasizing that quality practices may need to be tailored based on these contexts. For instance, a simple script should be managed differently from complex infrastructure software, guiding the development and evaluation processes accordingly.

This report draws on contributions from the EVERSE Task Force 2 (TF2), with foundational input from experts from different domains and institutions such as CERTH, OpenAIRE, BSC, and others in the subgroup focused on software quality. The input from these domain experts was crucial in shaping the quality dimensions, and their collective contributions helped establish the key quality categories necessary for listing tools.

According to EVERSE TF2 [6], software quality encompasses key dimensions, emphasizing "**Technical Aspects**", "**Openness**," "**Sustainability**," and alignment with the "**FAIR principles**" [5] (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable). These dimensions were further refined as detailed below in this section ([III.4.3](#) Adjustment of Attributes). The resulting dimensions will serve as the initial classification base for listing tools and services in this report and definitions are given in [Section IV](#).

2. Quality Attributes

Quality attributes were classified under each dimension, recognizing their function as specific subcategories that clarify and elaborate on the overarching quality dimensions. In this context, quality dimensions represent overarching principles, while quality attributes fall under these dimensions to provide a more specific categorization.

The method for categorizing quality attributes was based on a combined approach, integrating established standards, official guidelines, and expert contributions.

Initially, the [ISO/IEC 25010:2011\(E\)](#), revised by [ISO/IEC 25002:2024](#), [ISO/IEC 25010:2023](#) and [ISO/IEC 25019:2023](#) quality standards, provided a foundational reference for defining key software quality attributes. Building on this, along with two other sources—the [ISO/IEC/IEEE 24765:2017](#) standard and the [Design Fundamentals chapter of the Microsoft Application Architecture Guide](#) —the [EOSC review of quality attributes and characteristics](#) identified 25 characteristics and 126 quality attributes subdivided into six categories derived from their survey. The [Ensure Software Quality](#) report expanded on this by offering comprehensive technical and organizational recommendations for enhancing research software quality. This report, grounded in an extensive literature review, particularly emphasized software used in services provided through EOSC. It highlighted relevant quality attributes for research software and made targeted recommendations accordingly.

Complementing these efforts, official guidelines, such as [The FAIR for Research Software Principles](#) aim to promote and encourage the findability, accessibility, interoperability, and reusability (FAIR) of research software, ensuring that it can be sustainably maintained and widely used over time. The [OpenSSF](#) best practices focus on improving the security and hygiene of software development, encouraging [secure](#) coding practices. According to the EOSC review, standards, and guidelines, a technical notebook was created by a subgroup from the EVERSE TF2 to nominate the most mentioned and important software quality attributes.

This integrated approach, combining official definitions and expert input, provided a coherent and evidence-based framework for categorizing software quality attributes, tailored specifically to research software and open standards.

3. Adjustment of Attributes

During the analysis phase, redundancy was observed, especially in attributes that overlapped between the technical and sustainability dimensions.

To avoid duplication and improve clarity, overlapping attributes were reassigned to the sustainability dimension, acknowledging that technical quality is not an end in itself but serves a purpose. This adjustment led to the refinement of attributes previously considered to be part of the technical dimension and the emphasis on sustainability, resulting in the following categories:

- **Sustainability:** Functional Sustainability, Reproducibility, Long-term Usability, Portability, Maintainability, Documentation and Technical Support, Usability, Testing and Code Analysis, Security, Community Engagement, and Resource Efficiency.
- **FAIRness:** Attributes such as Findability, Accessibility, Interoperability, and Reusability.
- **Openness:** Open source Software and software transparency were consolidated under this category.

These categories are defined and explained in [Section IV](#).

4. Classification of survey results

Results from Miro board discussions and survey data were systematically categorized under these dimensions:

- **Source Code Management** was categorized under **Reproducibility** as part of **Sustainability**.
- **Packaging and Distribution** were categorized under **Portability** as part of **Sustainability**.
- **Continuous Integration/Deployment** was categorized under **Testing and Code analysis** as part of **Sustainability**.

IV. Results

This section details the attributes of the quality dimensions identified through the above process: Sustainability, FAIRness and Open Software. It accompanies each dimension with relevant tools and services that assess, curate and improve this aspect of software quality.

The initial collection of usable tools and services in the EOSC Science Clusters is available in a collaborative spreadsheet as a digital object. This document contains the name of the tool, its description and an access link, as well as the classification and other metadata on the licenses used. A snapshot of the document is attached at the end of the Deliverable.

A. Sustainability

Software sustainability refers to a set of principles and practices aimed at designing, developing and maintaining software that ensures long-term availability, adaptability and maintainability, minimizes the environmental impact and allows for the efficient use of resources. In doing so, it takes into account the entire life cycle of software, from development to deployment, use, and eventual retirement. Here, sustainability covers all aspects that contribute to sustainability, be it social or technical aspects. There exist a number of tools that assist in achieving the sustainability of software. These can be classified according to these key attributes they assess, curate and improve:

- *Functional Sustainability*: Help developers maintain and update their software over time.
- *Reproducibility*: Ensure that the results generated by a software are reliable, consistent and can be verified by others.
- *Long-term Usability*: The ability of a software to remain functional, maintainable and usable over an extended period of time, despite changes in technology, computing environments and user requirements.
- *Portability*: The ability of a software to be easily transferred, installed and run on different computing environments, platforms and architectures, with minimal modifications or adjustments.
- *Maintainability*: The software is designed to be modular, flexible and easy to update.
- *Documentation and Technical Support*
- *Usability*: How easy and efficient it is for researchers to use the software to accomplish their research tasks.
- *Testing*: Systematic process of evaluating and verifying software applications to ensure they meet specified requirements and function correctly.
- *Security*: Measures to ensure the confidentiality, integrity, and availability of research software.
- *Community*: The software project is designed to cultivate an active community.
- *Resource efficiency*: The software is designed to consume minimal energy and resources.

B. FAIRness

The FAIR principles for research software [4] were released in 2022 by the FAIR for Research Software (FAIR4RS) working group. They are a set of guidelines to make research software more Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable. The principles and acronym were first developed and adopted for scientific data management. However, due to the specific nature of software in terms of its executable nature, composition and continuous development,

the FAIR Data principles cannot be applied directly to software. Research data, for instance, is static and can only be supplemented with additional data collected. Software, on the other hand, is a growing construct on which many people are working on and of which there may be different versions. The FAIR4RS principles are:

- *Findability*: Software, and its associated metadata, is easy for both humans and machines to find.
- *Accessibility*: Software, and its metadata, are retrievable via standardised protocols.
- *Interoperability*: Software interoperates with other software by exchanging data and/or metadata, and/or through interaction via application programming interfaces (APIs), described through standards.
- *Reusability*: Software is both usable (can be executed) and reusable (can be understood, modified, built upon, or incorporated into other software).

C. Open Software

Open Software is a broad term encompassing any software that is freely available to the public and which also refers to the use of open standards or development models resulting in improved transparency. A more specific variant of Open Software is Open Source Software, that mainly focuses on the license of a software. Nevertheless, both terms are often used interchangeably, even though there is a subtle distinction between them. In general, all Open Source Software is Open Software, as it provides the freedom to access and modify the source code. However, not all Open Software is Open Source Software, as some may not have its source code readily available or may be subject to more restrictive licensing terms. There are several ways in which open software benefits research e.g. transparency is strengthened, collaboration is made easier and thus building community around a software is sometimes only made possible; helps with the verifiability and can also help in advancing the careers of scientists. Getting started in the world of Open Software is not always straight-forward, e.g. legal aspects need to be considered, and building community is a long-term endeavour. There are numerous tools that make it easier to get started and that help to assess, curate and improve in this regard.

V. Conclusion

In Deliverable 3.1 we outline the first steps taken towards reaching the WP3 objectives of

1. establishing a technology watch identifying and gathering tools and services targeting scientific software, code, and workflows quality and FAIRness as well as
2. assisting the EOSC Science Clusters in measuring and improving software, code, and workflows quality and FAIRness globally by combining existing tools and services into common frameworks.

Therefore, we first introduce the methods used to develop a categorization for the list of tools, and we explain how the tool collection was done. Building on this, a first collection of existing tools usable in the EOSC Science Clusters to assess, curate and improve software quality and FAIRness has been created. This list is provided as a collaborative digital document and is meant to be expanded and updated to reflect the dynamic set of tools available and the diverse application in different projects or areas.

As a next step, the list of tools is to be transferred into a machine-readable format that allows for the integration and presentation in RSQKit. The necessary preparatory work for creating the machine-readable list has already been initiated by the structured collection of metadata and assignment of categories. In addition, a further review and expansion of the initial collection by the EOSC Science Clusters will be necessary. We plan to expand the current list and evaluate it by conducting the survey among a wider group of people, e.g. the EOSC Science Clusters that also will be further involved in this process.

Thus, the efforts on structuring, classifying and categorizing, together with the initial collection of tools, serves as a solid basis for further refinement and coordination of the tool collection with the EOSC Science Clusters.

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